

Ferrofluid-Based Soft Electromagnetic Actuator

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Abstract. This paper explores the feasibility of using soft electromagnetic actuators incorporating ferrofluids as the primary mechanism for generating tactile feedback in wearable haptic interfaces. The distinctive feature of this research is the utilization of ferrofluid as a dynamic, adaptable medium, manipulated by electromagnetic fields to simulate tactile sensations. Preliminary experiments assess the feasibility, construction, and performance of these actuators, focusing on their capacity to provide controlled vibrations at desired frequencies and amplitudes. Results indicate that the actuator gives a total displacement of 1mm during vibration. The actuator provides a steady amplitude with cutoff occurring at 30Hz.

Keywords: Haptics · Vibrotactile · Soft Robotics · Ferrofluidics

1 Introduction

Haptic interfaces are at the forefront of wearable technology innovation, aiming to create devices that are thin, lightweight, and capable of integrating seamlessly as skin-like systems across various body regions [2]. These devices strive to enhance user experience by providing artificial touch sensations through mechanical vibrations without impeding natural movement. The ideal haptic interface is aesthetically pleasing and conforms to the body's natural contours, avoiding bulky designs that could restrict flexibility or comfort [4]. Achieving this integration poses significant challenges, particularly when the actuators involved are typically large and rigid [2].

1.1 Current State of Wearable Haptic Technologies

The landscape of haptic technologies is characterized by a diverse range of actuators, each engineered to meet specific requirements of wearable devices. Electromagnetic Actuators, including Eccentric Rotating Mass (ERM) motors and Linear Resonant Actuators (LRA), are prevalent in commercial applications due to their compact size, and energy efficiency. However, both ERM and LRA actuators are relatively heavy and bulky, and constructed from materials not inherently soft, posing challenges for integration into flexible wearable systems [4]. As the focus shifts towards the development of soft actuators suitable for wearable technology, several innovative options emerge.

Piezoelectric actuators consist of a thin layer of piezoelectric material between two electrodes, allowing vertical movement and force production when a voltage is applied. Despite their precise control and quick response, they are limited by their inability to adjust their natural vibration frequency [4]. Soft Pneumatic Actuators (SPA) utilize air transferred into a deformable bladder, valued for their structural advantages especially

in tight spaces or on sensitive regions of the body [1][2]. The ongoing challenge in the field is enhancing these technologies to achieve greater integration, reduced size, and increased responsiveness to meet the intricate demands of wearable technology.

1.2 Research Objective

This paper introduces a novel approach involving soft electromagnetic actuators that utilize coils and ferrofluid materials to overcome the existing limitations. The hypothesis is that such actuators can provide adaptable tactile feedback, enhancing user interactions. This research focuses on the feasibility, construction, and performance testing of these wearable electromagnetic actuators designed to improve haptic feedback across various real-world applications. The actuator incorporates an electromagnet and ferrofluid sandwiched between layers of thin film silicone, creating vibrations through an electric field that are quantifiable in terms of frequency and amplitude. Existing electromagnetic actuators incorporate ferrofluid into their design. Yet, none have developed wearable actuators where ferrofluid itself acts as the moving agent causing the vibrations [3]. Ferrofluid is advantageous due to its adaptable nature and super paramagnetic properties. When encapsulated in silicone, it can stretch and conform without losing these properties, making it an ideal choice for haptic interfaces.

2 Methodology and Results

Silicone was spread using a thin film spreader to form a uniform base layer. A circular piece of tape was then placed on this base layer. A second layer of silicone was applied over it. Each layer is 5 μm thick. This approach allowed the silicone layers outside the tape to cure together while the tape itself created an internal pocket. After the silicone had cured, ferrofluid was injected into the pocket formed by the tape using a syringe needle. The actuation system included a 5V electromagnet with an 8 kg holding force, positioned 10 mm from the silicone membrane. This electromagnet was used to induce displacement through electromagnetic fields. Testing involved pulsing the electromagnet at various frequencies and voltages to study the membrane's displacement. Displacement was measured using an Acuity AR200 laser measurement sensor, which provided accurate data on the movement of the membrane and the behavior of the ferrofluid under different electromagnetic conditions, Figure 1a).

The electromagnet was operated at 5 volts, while the pulsing frequency was varied to assess the dynamic behavior of the thin film actuator. Figure 1b) shows the Bode magnitude plot of displacements to input voltage. It was observed that the actuator maintained a consistent displacement amplitude of 1 mm up to the 3dB cutoff frequency of 30Hz. Beyond this frequency, the amplitude drops at the rate of about 12db/octave. The phase shift of the Bode plot was calculated by measuring the delay between the input signal and the complete displacement, defined by the 0-100% rise time. The phase shift starts at 0 degrees and decreases to around -180 degrees at the cutoff frequency. This occurs because, at higher frequencies, the actuator's response time lags significantly behind the input signal. By the time the actuator starts responding, it is already receiving an opposite command, causing a substantial phase lag.

Fig. 1. (a) The assembled actuator setup showing the electromagnet, thin film actuator, and laser sensor used to measure displacement. (b) Bode plot illustrating the response of the actuator, with a steady amplitude of 1 mm up to a 3dB cutoff frequency of 30 Hz.

3 Future Work

The results represent a promising step forward in the development of soft vibrotactile actuators. The thinness of the silicone layers, along with the chemical interactions between the magnetite nanoparticles and the silicone, alter the actuator's dynamic characteristics. Future testing will need to focus on how these variations in ferrofluid composition affect the actuator response, providing valuable insights for optimizing performance in practical applications. The next steps in this research involve significant advancements in the design and integration of the actuator system. The current prototype employs a rather bulky, rigid electromagnet, emphasizing the need for enhancements towards miniaturization and flexibility. The plan includes developing a stretchable coil that can conform more effectively to natural body movements, enhancing both comfort and functionality. Ultimately, the goal is to integrate these components into a unified system that maintains the dynamic properties necessary for effective tactile simulation.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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